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Experimental Investigation of Mechanical Properties of GFRP–Hemp Fibre Hybrid Epoxy Composites

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, hybrid composites are gaining attention due to improved properties and partial replacement of synthetic materials. In this study, hybrid epoxy composites were developed by combining glass fibre with hemp fibre using the hand lay-up method. In the present work, the main aim is to evaluate the mechanical behaviour of the hybrid composite in comparison with conventional GFRP. The specimens were tested for tensile, compressive, and impact properties. Under tensile loading, the hybrid composite reached 162 MPa, while the GFRP sample was about 133 MPa. This is roughly a 21.8% increase. The same behaviour was observed across the samples. In compression, the hybrid composite showed a value of 1.196 MPa compared to 0.130 MPa for GFRP. The difference is quite large. At the same time, the overall values are still low, which may be related to fabrication issues such as void formation or weak fibre–matrix bonding. For impact testing, the hybrid composite recorded an average of 6.67 J, whereas the baseline value was close to 6 J. The variation is small, indicating only a limited improvement in impact behaviour. From the overall results, it is observed that the hybrid composite performs better in tensile loading. The improvement in compressive and impact properties is not very high. The study shows that hemp fibre can be used as a secondary reinforcement. The final performance mainly depends on the fabrication quality.

Keywords: GFRP, hemp fibre, natural fibre composites, hand lay-up, tensile strength, compressive strength, impact resistance, water absorption

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, composite materials are widely used in many engineering fields due to their ability to provide good strength and low weight. Their properties can be controlled by selecting suitable matrix and reinforcement materials. Among different types of composites, glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) is widely used because of its high strength-to-weight ratio, corrosion resistance, and low cost [1, 2].

However, when epoxy is used as the matrix, some limitations are observed. The material is brittle and does not absorb much energy under impact loading. Because of this, researchers have tried combining it with natural fibres. This can improve toughness and also reduce weight and environmental impact [3, 4].

Hemp fibre is one of the natural fibres that has gained attention in recent years. It shows good mechanical properties due to its high cellulose content. Compared to some other natural fibres, it also offers better processability [5]. In addition, hemp is biodegradable and renewable, and it requires less chemical treatment. This makes it suitable for sustainable applications [6, 7].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Natural fibres are used in polymer composites mainly because of sustainability, low cost, and acceptable mechanical performance. Many studies have reported improvements in processing and material behaviour over the years. Faruk et al. [7] discussed developments in this area and reported better fibre treatment and fabrication methods. They also mentioned problems like moisture absorption and weak bonding between fibre and matrix.

Hemp fibre is one of the natural fibres that has gained attention in recent years. It shows good mechanical properties mainly due to its high cellulose content. Compared to some other natural fibres, it also offers better processability [5]. In addition, hemp is biodegradable and renewable, and it requires less chemical treatment. This makes it suitable for sustainable applications [6, 7].

Many studies are available on natural fibre composites such as jute, sisal, and flax. But work on hybrid composites combining hemp fibre with GFRP under the same testing conditions is still limited. Most of the existing studies focus on individual properties. Combined evaluation of tensile, compressive, impact, and water absorption behaviour is not widely reported.

In this study, hybrid GFRP-hemp fibre composites are prepared using the hand lay-up method. The specimens are tested according to ASTM standards. The main aim is to evaluate tensile strength, compressive strength, impact behaviour, and water absorption of the hybrid composite and compare it with conventional GFRP. The study also focuses on understanding whether the hybrid composite can be used for lightweight structural applications. Some work has focused on improving bonding. Surface treatment, especially alkali treatment, is found to improve fibre–matrix interaction. This results in better tensile and flexural properties [9]. Fibre structure and lignin content also affect performance, which is important in the case of hemp fibre [10].

In hybrid composites, natural fibres are combined with glass fibre to balance strength and weight. Increasing glass fibre content improves strength, but it also increases weight. So, the final behaviour

depends on the fibre ratio and application [6].

For hemp fibre, studies have shown good tensile behaviour and improved impact response due to its ductile nature. Fibre treatment and structure also influence the final properties [8].

Even with these studies, work on hemp–GFRP hybrid composites under the same testing conditions is still limited. Combined evaluation of tensile, compressive, impact, and water absorption behaviour is not widely reported.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Raw Materials

In this study, three main materials were used: glass fibre, hemp fibre and epoxy resin system. Glass fibre (E-glass) was used as the primary reinforcement because of its high strength and stiffness. Hemp

fibre was used as a natural reinforcement to reduce weight and improve sustainability.

The epoxy resin (LY556) with HY951 hardener was used as the matrix. The resin and hardener were mixed in 10:1 weight ratio.

The hemp fibres were treated using 5% NaOH solution for about 2 hours at room temperature. This treatment helps in removing impurities and improves bonding between fibre and matrix. After treatment, the fibres were washed and dried before use.

Laminate Configurations

Three types of laminates were prepared by varying the fibre composition. The total fibre content was maintained constant while changing the amount of hemp fibre.

The configurations used are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Laminate configuration and composition.

Sample ID	Glass fibre (wt.%)	Hemp fibre (wt.%)	Epoxy + Hardener (wt.%)	Stacking sequence
S1	60	0	40	GF/GF/GF
S2	50	10	40	GF/HF/GF
S3	45	15	40	GF/HF/HF/GF

Fabrication

The laminates were prepared using hand lay-up method in a flat mould. The mould surface was cleaned and coated with release agent. The resin and hardener were mixed properly. Fibre layers were placed one by one according to the stacking sequence. Resin was applied between each layer to ensure proper wetting. A roller

was used to remove trapped air. After stacking, pressure was applied using weight to maintain thickness and remove voids. The laminate was cured at room temperature for 24 hours. Post curing was then carried out at about 60°C for 2 hours. Finally, the laminates were removed and cut into required specimen sizes using cutting tools as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Fabricated composite samples before failure. (a) Tensile sample (b) Compression sample (c) Impact sample (d) Water Absorption sample

Testing Methods

The prepared composite specimens were tested for tensile, compressive, impact, and water absorption behaviour using standard testing procedures.

Tensile testing

Tensile testing was carried out using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM) as per ASTM D3039 standard. The specimens were prepared according to the required dimensions.

The test was conducted at a constant loading rate until failure. During the test, load and displacement were recorded. The maximum load obtained was used to calculate tensile strength.

Compressive testing

Compressive testing was performed using UTM as per ASTM standards. The specimen was placed properly in the fixture to ensure uniform loading.

The load was applied gradually until failure occurred. The maximum load recorded during the test was used to calculate compressive strength.[11]

Impact testing

Impact testing was carried out using a Charpy impact testing machine. The specimens were prepared with standard dimensions.

The energy absorbed by the specimen during fracture was recorded directly from

the machine. This value represents the impact strength of the material.

Water absorption test

Water absorption behaviour was studied as per ASTM D570 standard. The specimens were first dried and weighed to obtain the initial weight.

The samples were then immersed in water at room temperature for 72 hours. After immersion, the specimens were removed, wiped to remove surface moisture, and weighed again.[12]

The percentage of water absorption was calculated based on the weight difference before and after immersion as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Tested Specimens of Fabricated composite samples after failure. (a) Tensile tested sample (b) Compression tested sample (c) Impact tested sample (d) Water Absorption tested sample.

Calculation of Mechanical Properties

The mechanical properties were calculated using the maximum load obtained from experimental testing and standard stress relations.

Cross-sectional area

For compression specimens:

- Width = 50 mm
- Thickness = 3 mm

$$A = 50 \times 3 = 150 \text{ mm}^2$$

For tensile specimens:

$$A = 30 \text{ mm}^2$$

Tensile strength

Tensile strength was calculated using:

$$\sigma_t = \frac{P}{A}$$

GFRP

$$P = 3990 \text{ N}$$
$$\sigma_t = \frac{3990}{30} = 133 \text{ MPa}$$

Hybrid composite

$$P = 4860 \text{ N}$$
$$\sigma_t = \frac{4860}{30} = 162 \text{ MPa}$$

Compressive Strength

Compressive strength was calculated using:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{A}$$

GFRP

$$P = 0.9 \text{ kN} = 900 \text{ N}$$
$$\sigma_c = \frac{900}{150} = 6 \text{ MPa}$$

Hybrid composite

$$P = 1.196 \text{ kN} = 1196 \text{ N}$$
$$\sigma_c = \frac{1196}{150} = 7.97 \text{ MPa} \approx 8 \text{ MPa}$$

Impact Strength

Impact strength values were obtained directly from the testing machine:

- GFRP = **6 J**
- Hybrid composite = **6.67 J**

Water Absorption

Water absorption was calculated using:

$$\%W = \frac{W_2 - W_1}{W_1} \times 100$$

where:

$$W_1 = 1.5 \text{ g}$$
$$W_2 = 1.527 \text{ g}$$
$$\%W = \frac{1.527 - 1.5}{1.5} \times 100 = 1.8\%$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The experimental results for tensile, compressive, impact, and water absorption behaviour are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of experimental results.

Property	GFRP	Hybrid Composite
Tensile Strength (MPa)	133	162
Compressive Strength (MPa)	6	8
Impact Strength (J)	6	6.67
Water Absorption (%)	1.95	1.8

Tensile Properties

Table 3. Tensile Test Results.

Specimen	Area (mm ²)	Load (N)	Strength (MPa)
GFRP	30	3990	133
Hybrid	30	4860	162

The hybrid composite shows a clear increase in tensile strength compared to GFRP. The value increased from 133 MPa to 162 MPa, which is about 21.8% improvement as shown in Table 3.

This behaviour indicates that load transfer between fibres is more effective in the hybrid system. Glass fibre carries the major load, while hemp fibre contributes by delaying crack propagation. The

presence of hemp fibre creates local resistance to crack growth, which increases the overall strength as shown in Figure 3.

However, the improvement is not only due to fibre addition. It also depends on fibre distribution and bonding quality. If the bonding is weak, fibre pull-out occurs earlier and reduces strength.

Fig. 3: Comparison of ultimate tensile strength of GFRP and hybrid composite.

Compressive properties

Table 4: Compressive Test Results.

Specimen	Area (mm ²)	Load (kN)	Strength (MPa)
GFRP	150	0.9	6
Hybrid	150	1.196	8

The compressive strength shows an increase from 6 MPa to 8 MPa. This is

around 33% improvement as shown in Table 4.

But unlike tensile behaviour, the values are still relatively low. This indicates that compressive performance is not fully improved by hybridisation as shown in Figure 4.

The main reason is the presence of defects. Under compression, voids and weak

bonding regions act as stress concentration points. These regions promote local buckling and early failure.

Also, hemp fibre is not as strong as glass fibre in compression. So even though there is some improvement, the behaviour is still dominated by defects and fibre properties.

Fig. 4: Comparison of compressive strength of GFRP and hybrid composite.

Impact properties

Table 5: Impact Test Results.

Specimen	Impact Energy (J)
GFRP	6
Hybrid	6.67

Only a small increase is observed in impact strength. The hybrid composite shows 6.67 J compared to 6 J as shown in Table 5

This suggests that the energy absorption mechanism is not significantly improved. Ideally, hemp fibre should improve impact

resistance through fibre pull-out and crack deflection.

However, this requires good fibre–matrix bonding. In the present case, the limited improvement indicates that bonding is not strong enough to fully utilize the fibre pull-out mechanism as shown in Figure 5.

Fig. 5: Comparison of impact strength of GFRP and hybrid composite.

Water Absorption Behaviour

Table 6: Water Absorption Results.

Specimen	Initial (g)	Final (g)	Absorption (%)
Hybrid	1.5	1.527	1.8

The hybrid composite shows 1.8% water absorption after 48 hours as shown in Table 6.

This behaviour is mainly influenced by hemp fibre. Natural fibres are hydrophilic, so they tend to absorb moisture. The absorption occurs through fibre–matrix

interfaces and micro-voids present in the laminate.

At the same time, the epoxy matrix limits excessive moisture penetration. Because of this, the overall absorption remains moderate as shown in Figure 6.

Fig. 6: Water absorption comparison after 48 hours.

CONCLUSION

In this work, hybrid composite laminates were prepared by combining glass fibre and hemp fibre in an epoxy matrix using the hand lay-up process. The aim was to see how the addition of a natural fibre changes the behaviour compared to a conventional GFRP laminate.

From the tensile results, a clear improvement was observed. The hybrid composite reached 162 MPa, while the GFRP sample showed 133 MPa. This increase is noticeable and consistent across the samples. It suggests that the two fibre types are working together to carry the load, rather than acting separately.

In compression, the hybrid composite showed a higher value compared to GFRP. However, the overall strength is still low. This is likely due to fabrication-related

issues such as voids and uneven bonding. These factors become more critical under compressive loading.

For impact behaviour, the change is small. The hybrid composite showed 6.67 J compared to 6 J for GFRP. This indicates that the energy absorption capability is not significantly improved in the current configuration.

Water absorption was found to be around 1.8% for the hybrid composite and about 2% for GFRP. The difference is not very large, but the hybrid shows slightly lower absorption. This may be related to better packing or fewer voids in the laminate.

Overall, the hybrid composite performs better in tensile loading, while improvements in compression and impact are limited. The results also show that

fabrication quality has a strong influence on the final properties.

So, the material can be considered suitable for applications where tensile loading is dominant. At the same time, improving the fabrication process could further enhance the overall performance.

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